

schoenobii Ferriere were the only egg parasites obtained from 193 egg masses (1,070 eggs) of *S. incertulas* (see table). Although *Telenomus* sp. caused a higher percentage of parasitization than *T. schoenobii* in all four generations (*S. incertulas* completes two generations each cropping season in Sri Lanka), the difference was not significant. □

Parasitization of *S. incertulas* eggs by *Telenomus* sp. and *T. schoenobii*. Maha Illuppallama, Sri Lanka, May and Jul, 1982.

Generation	Eggs (no.)	Parasitization (%)		
		<i>Telenomus</i> sp.	<i>T. schoenobii</i>	Total
1st	208	27.0	17.3	44.3
2d	195	27.4	16.0	43.4
3d	345	36.3	24.5	60.8
4th	322	35.3	23.3	58.6

Diluted quinalphos and fenthion and control of whitebacked planthopper (WBPH)

J. Singh and S.S. Malhi, Plant Breeding Department, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana, India

Two experiments with two insecticides (quinalphos and fenthion) were conducted to evaluate diluted insecticides in controlling WBPH *Sogatella furcifera* at Bhupindra Rice Research Substation, Rauni, 1985 wet season.

Recommended rate (0.5 kg ai/ha) of quinalphos and fenthion was diluted with water to apply 250, 375, and 500 liters/ha. A randomized block design with four replications for quinalphos and three for fenthion was used. Plot size was 300 m².

WBPH counts at 2 and 8 d after application for quinalphos and 2 d after application for fenthion showed no significant differences among treatments (see table). □

Effect of diluted insecticides on WBPH incidence. Punjab, India, 1985.

Treatment	WBPH ^a (adults + nymphs)/10 hills		
	Pre-treatment ^b	2 d after application	8 d after application
Quinalphos 25 EC			
250	174 a	11 a	80 a
375	171 a	9 a	84 a
500	174 a	4 a	101 a
Control	184 a	200 b	273 b
Fenthion 1000 EC			
250	211 a	11 a	—
375	189 a	9 a	—
500	175 a	10 a	—
Control	182 a	294 b	—

^aFor each group of insecticide treatments, means in a column followed by a common letter do not differ significantly at the 5% level by DMRT. ^b30 Aug for quinalphos and 5 Sep for fenthion.

***Nisaga simplex* caterpillar on rice in western Orissa**

N. C. Patnaik, Entomology Department, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology (OUAT), Bhubaneswar - 3; B. Mohanty, Regional Research Station (RRS), Bhanwanipatna; and A. K. Parida, AICRP on Weed Control, OUAT; Bhubaneswar - 3, India

Hairy caterpillar *Nisaga simplex* Wlk. (Eupterotidae: Lepidoptera) regularly damages upland and medium ricefields in various locations of Kalahandi and Koraput districts in the wet season Jun-Dec. Moths emerged in Jun with the onset of the monsoon and oviposit on weedy growth of scrubby jungles and on adjoining ricefields. Incubation lasted 7-9 d. In the laboratory, 8 larval instars were completed in 68-76 d. Pupation took place in soil. Caterpillars fed

voraciously on the leaf lamina, leaving only the midrib.

In its natural habitat, the pest pupated in loose lateritic soil, often as deep as 30 cm, in Oct and overwintered to the following Jun. The caterpillars shunned water and did not migrate to lowland fields. The moths are poor fliers.

Weedy fields attracted higher populations than weeded fields. The caterpillars also attacked maize, sorghum, finger millet, sugarcane, and these weed species: *Brachiaria mutica*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Dactyloctenium aegyptium*, *Digitaria ciliaris*, *Echinochloa colona*, *E. crus-galli*, *E. glabrescens*, *Eleusine indica*, *Ischaemum rugosum*, *Leersia hexandra*, *Leptochloa chinensis*, *Panicum repens*, *Paspalum conjugatum*, *P. clisticum*, and *P. scrobiculatum*. □

Rice leaffolder (LF) infestations in West Bengal

P. B. Chatterjee, Rice Research Station, P.O. Chinsurah R.S. 712102, Hooghly, West Bengal, India

Rice LF generally appears as a minor pest of rice in West Bengal. However, it

infested over 67,000 ha in 11 districts in 1986, causing appreciable damage to standing wet season rice. All the districts experiencing massive infestation were located on the south and southwest sides of the river Ganges.

Cnaphalocrocis medinalis (Guenée) was the most dominant LF species;

Leaves damaged by LF, maximum and minimum temperatures, and rainfall in different months.^a West Bengal, India.

Month	Damaged leaves (%)	Mean monthly temperature (°C)		Rainfall (mm)
		Maximum	Minimum	
May	3.6	34.5 (-1.9)	22.3 (-2.7)	178.8 (+63.4)
Jun	5.5	34.3 (+0.4)	26.6 (+1.1)	278.6 (+30.0)
Jul	12.6	31.5 (-0.2)	25.9 (+0.2)	249.5 (-40.2)
Aug	31.3	32.7 (+1.4)	26.3 (+0.6)	98.2 (-404.4)
Sep	73.6	31.4 (-0.1)	25.1 (-0.4)	750.0 (+513.5)
Oct	31.9	30.6 (-0.4)	22.1 (-0.8)	104.3 (-8.0)

^aMean of 20 samples. Figures in the parentheses indicate deviations from normal.